

Original Research Article

Employee Development as Determinant of Job Performance in Selected Money Deposit Banks in Nigeria

Sunday Moses Adeyemi*, Akinbo M. Tina

Abstract

Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: msaconsult@ymail.com

This study examined the relationship between employee development and job performance of selected money deposit banks in Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design which is explanatory in nature to obtain responses from the deposit money banks, Nigeria. The Taro Yamane sample size derivation formula was used to determine the sample size. After data cleaning, 165 respondents were finally used for data analysis. Data for the study was collected through structured questionnaires while the five (5) point Likert scale was used to measure the responses from the respondents. The reliability of the study was determined using the Cronbach alpha coefficient. Spearman's Rank Order Correlation coefficient Statistics technique was used to test the hypotheses with the aid of statistical package for Social Science Version 25.0 for the purposes of examining the nature and proposed associations. The findings revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between employee development and job performance in the deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study concludes that career development has a strong positive and significant influence on the two measures of employee job performance in the deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that Deposit money banks should implement career development policies towards effective succession planning. Management should exhaust all internal talent before considering external talent especially when making promotion as this can significantly impact the overall development achievement.

Keywords: Career development, Employee Development, Job Performance

INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

The Nigerian banking system has undergone remarkable changes over the years in terms of the number of institutions ownership, structure, technological innovation, expansion, and number of local and international branches, capital base, among others (Ekerete, 2005).

For a long time, financial service providers had presumed that their operations were customer-centric, simply because they had customers and were able to generate profits. However, in the current era of hyper competition, where only a very slight difference exists in the services provided by the major players in this industry, their services need skilled expertise and committed employees

to meet customers' demands in the industry. The need to improve employee development in the banking industry has become a universally accepted phenomenon that depends on efficient and effective job development. It has become necessary, in view of the modern global corporate world to invest in socialization, mentoring and professional skills to build employee confidence in any organizational setting.

Oyewumi, Ibitoye and Sanni (2012) stated that skilled, professional, committed and efficient workers play a vital role in achieving the goals in an organization. Workforce is long lasting and very important asset of any organization as it manages other assets and activities of the organization. Williams & Anderson (1991) sees job performance as a work related outcome or activity that demonstrates how well these activities are accomplished by the individual workers in the organization. Developing human resources is viewed as a process of finding and bringing together more people who possess the knowledge, skills, and experience necessary for a country's economic growth to increase its population. In addition, the banking industry's discourse on human resource development methods focuses on increasing the staff's skills, inventiveness, and technical competence to increase productivity and employee retention. However, employers must also enhance their intrinsic resources to be more competent and effective in managing physical and other human resources if the idea of training and development methods is not confined just to workers' interests. To face the challenges of today's dynamism of business and the expanding worldwide interconnectedness of financial operations, banks, in particular, must invest heavily in training and development.

Employee job performance has been described in many ways; ability to achieve targets, realize goals, attain benchmarks. Most commonly people immediately talked of job performance as what a person did at work. Different stages of a job as well the complexity of a job also affected the overall performance of the jobholder (Adim, Ibekwe & Akintokunbo, 2018). An employee's performance is observed at work and determined during job performance evaluation, with an employer taking into consideration components such as quality of work, quantity of work, cooperativeness or loyalty, resourcefulness and reliability, conduct, self-development or improvement efforts and experience to analyze each employee based on his or her merit. Adeyemo (2010) stated that naturally a worker who possesses a high skill level such as unique skills, intelligence and work methods will succeed in his or her job.

In the banking industry, employees' job performance is very important because it will reflect on the organizations' performance. Employee performance standards were designed by the organization to measure the performance of the industry. Therefore, job performance becomes the most important focus of workers and

academicians because the performance level will deteriorate if the level of skill of employee drops and it is generally believed that employees are the "backbones" of the corporate world (Fauzilah, Noryati & Zaharah, 2011). Hence, managers have given more concern about managing tasks and contextual performance of their employees. Researchers have also identified different factors that can affect job performance. In the last two decades, banking conditions have also changed drastically (Khilji, 2006). Organizations are now promoting a culture of learning and development to improve their human resources to create a competitive edge (Johnson, Pepper, Adkins, & Emejom, 2018). Career management is a system which is organized, formalized and it's a planned effort of achieving a balance between the individual career needs and the organization's workforce requirements (Leibowitz et al., 2006). The rapidly growing awareness makes it obvious that people can give the firm its leading edge in the market place. Career management practices are the core function of human resource management which develops the short and long-term capacity of employees. Career management practices are key strategic considerations for all organizations regardless of market or profile. The management of the capacity and capability of the organization managers has a fundamental impact on efficiency, effectiveness, morale and profitability of an organization (Armstrong, 2001).

Various alternative components have been advanced as underpinning employee development. According to Kaya and Ceylan (2014) employee development encompasses development of abilities, maintenance of existing skills, and sharpening skills for the future. The commonality among the various definitions of career development is that they all focus on empowering an individual through development of hidden talent and skills. Whereas earlier definitions of employee development have tended to place emphasis on activities performed by the individual, later definitions have taken cognizance of the importance of professions in human resource matters in the entire process (Baruch, Szűcs, & Gunz, 2015). Many studies of employee development have failed to look fundamentally at how individuals manage their careers vi-a-vis the organization's goals, and how organizations structure members' career progress. Therefore, the purpose of the study is to examine employee development as determinant of job performance in selected money deposit banks in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

Career development

Career development is a critical element that facilitates individual goal achievement (Kraimer et al., 2011). Career development refers to whether people were

proud of their work, whether their superiors were satisfied with the work, and whether people felt comfortable in their jobs. Amundsen and Martinsen (2015) argued that employees' development activities and development created a positive career attitude in workers, which in turn could improve worker performance. Career development aims to encourage and build a career path which offers diversified mobility. Holbeche (2009) noted that career development is an individual-focused strategy that enhances individuals as well as organizational performance by providing training opportunities. Hall-Ellis (2015) stated that choosing a qualified and well trained individual for a key leadership position is a critical decision due to its potential influence on current and future organizational outcomes. Moreover, professional development opportunities reinforce succession planning strategies in the organization.

Career development activities are important particularly for new employees who enter the organization to build the capabilities appropriate for the workplace. Career development offers various learning opportunities to perform their jobs better which in turn enable the organization as

a whole to enhance performance. Empirical studies such as Ngo et al. (1998); Chand and Katou (2007) have found training and development is positively related with organization performance. Chand and Katou (2007) used sales growth, productivity, profitability, goal achievement, good services; and Ngo (1980) used sales, net profit, and development of new product/services to measure performance in their studies. Performance measures of our model have similarity with the performance measures of these studies.

Employee Job Performance

Employee job performance is now becoming an everyday watch word in modern organizations because of the activities and roles performed by individual workers in the workplace. It is crucial to the welfare of the industrial firm as well as for the economic progress of the country. Today, the term performance has acquired a wider meaning. The Oxford Advanced Learner Dictionary of Current English stressed that the word performance is a coinage of the old French word *parfournir* and it denotes, functioning, implementation, feat, and accomplishment. Timpson (2011) defined employee performance as the accomplishment of a given task measure against a preset known standard of acquiring competences, cost, and speed. In the same vein, O'clan (2012) defined employee performance as the fulfillment of an obligation in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract.

The aforesaid definitions lay emphasis on the importance of standard and the fulfillment of a designed task as cardinal issues in performance. However, the

yardstick and how it could be measured was ignored. In the words of Abbott (2012) employee job performance is an assessment of how well the process of carrying a task and how successfully its aims are accomplished. It produces, assembles and delivers on time and without wastage i.e. the best standard set for an employee to enable the actualization of organization goals and objective. This definition also tally with the view of Kelly (2013) who also sees employee performance as an accomplishment expected of employees to stimulate the achievement of organization goals and objectives. Bello (2013) viewed employee performance as the best effort, ability, and capability on a job, the accomplishment of organization tasks and the relationship between standard and the resources employed.

Task Accomplishment

Task accomplishment is a measure of an employee's job performance which involves their contribution to overall organizational productivity and actions that are part of the formal reward system and addresses the prescription as indicated in the descriptions of the role (Williams & Karau, 1991). It shows the level or the extent an employee achieves a given target. In general, task accomplishment comprises activities that translate the organizations policies, missions and resources into tangible and intangible goods produced by the organization and to enable efficient operation of the organization (Motowidlo, 1997).

Thus, task accomplishment covers the fulfillment of the requirements that are part of the agreement between the employee and the organization. Borman and Motowidlo (1993) pointed out

that task accomplishment is the effectiveness and efficiency with which job incumbents perform activities that contribute to the organization's technical core and assist in moulding the psychological state of the organization (Borman and Motowidlo, 1993). They further suggested that in accomplishing a given task there are two aspects to it, which are interpersonal facilitation and job dedication. Interpersonal facilitation includes cooperative and helpful acts that help the effectiveness of co-employee.

Training and Development

Formal training and development is considered any endeavor to enhance existing or prospective workers by enhancing their ability via learning, generally by a change in attitude or an increase in skills and knowledge. Training is defined as teaching specific abilities, whereas development refers to the learning opportunities meant to assist people in growing professionally. To train someone, you must first educate, instruct, develop, and

arrange for that person's future experiences. Organizational goals may be achieved more effectively when the interests of the organization and the personnel are integrated via training. To have a greater impact on performance, training must be well-designed and delivered (Borman & Motowidlo, 1993).

Employee performance can only be improved with proper training. Effective training and development programs are critical to organizational commitment or "the relative degree of an individual's identification and participation in a specific organization." Organizations that have a keen understanding of their workforce's training requirements develop plans to meet those needs. Investing in staff training leads to measurable gains in communication and performance expertise, as well as a longer period of employee retention. There are also substantial gains in profit and a higher proportion of reported pleasant working relationships when programs focus on communication skills with coworkers. Evidence suggests that education and training improve work performance, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. In addition, insufficient work training can lead to poor performance analyses, leading to dissatisfaction and conflict among employees.

More money spent on training and development will aid all firms in retaining more staff. A firm that invests in education and training will gain a competitive advantage, increase productivity, and increase employee loyalty. To a great extent, this is because training and development, whether or not it is a top priority for the company, is viewed as important to employee development (Borman & Motowidlo, 1993). This is true even if employee retention is not an urgent concern. Training will only become more critical as operational models like "The Learning Organization" or "Knowledge-Based Organization" continue to gain traction in today's corporate environment. It doesn't matter how you look at it, retention shows a desire to hold on to your best employees, but it's also about maintaining and managing the talents a company needs to succeed. To begin with, providing training is a way to help people improve their abilities. A powerful company model results from offering what recipients value highly and reaping the rewards as a result.

Given the importance of training and development, it defies logic to imply that these tools should be seen solely as "retention" measures. We've only come across a few instances when skill development at work has been explicitly introduced as a means of keeping employees. Despite this, many research have shown that employee happiness or discontent is often tied to concerns around their professional growth. Over 40% of small business employees are unsatisfied with the quantity of training they receive, according to a recent survey. According to the study, dissatisfaction and annoyance with the lack of possibilities to improve skills were strongly correlated with both an employee's desire

to quit and the frequency of absences. Gallup ranked the inability to develop and progress professionally as one of the top three factors for employee dissatisfaction in 1955. Other investigations have come to the same conclusion. Furthermore, all of the recommendations agree that the relationship between training and employee retention is especially strong for highly qualified workers Kelly (2013).

Workers should be trained to create an impact that will last long after the training activity or program has ended. It's critical for employees to focus on integrating newly learned abilities and concepts into their work environment by taking particular actions, choices, processes, and duties. Refers to an organization's official, unwavering effort and commitment to continually improve its personnel's performance level and happiness through different ways of skills development and educational programs. These initiatives have already taken on a broad and diversified shape in most organizations, encompassing anything from job-specific training to long-term career advancement. A key strategic instrument utilized in implementing policies that help an organization achieve its vision, purpose, goals, and objectives is training and career development, which has now manifested as an official corporate function. To help their employees advance and secure highly trained personnel, companies of all sizes have recognized the importance of education. They have included elements such as continuous learning and career development to help their employees progress.

Motivation

When we talk about motivation, we're talking about the factors inside or outside of ourselves that spur us on to action Kelly (2013). As a result, motivation is the desire and capacity of an individual to expend high amounts of effort to achieve an organization's objectives. According to their findings, motivation results from three major factors: effort, organizational objectives, and requirements of the individual or organization. Employee motivation is critical to the success of any organization. It's one of the five things that decide whether or not a company will survive, since it puts motivation on an equal footing with other things like money, machinery, and morale. Knowing what motivates workers is critical, since the success of any business relies on having a team that is both pleased and motivated. The effectiveness of managers is influenced by a variety of factors, including their level of motivation. They think that motivation produces energy and regulates a person's conduct, which is why they see it as the engine and the steering wheel of a vehicle. Because if we can figure out what drives a worker, we'll know what buttons to push to get him to work harder, what levers to pull to get him to alter his behavior, and what incentives to utilize to influence his views.

Any study of motivation must begin with a definition of the word "motivation." However, despite many attempts to define motivation, there does not seem to be widespread consensus among scholars about what the word should mean. There's a chance this is because the definitions reflect the authors' personal views and experiences in a particular field of study. We get the word motivational-ness "from the Latin word "movere" (meaning "to go") Amundsen and Martinsen (2015). However, this explains just a small part of the motivational process. "Motivation is the internal drive required to steer people's activities and behaviors toward the accomplishment of certain objectives,". The desire to fulfill specific demands and expectations is the source of this motivation or energy Holbeche (2009).

Motive is defined as "what possibly motivates someone to behave in a particular manner or at the very least acquire a predisposition for certain behavior,". The connection between needs, drives, and incentives holds the key to understanding motivation as a process. He defines motivation as a "process that begins with a physiological or psychological deficit that triggers action or a desire toward a goal or reward Amundsen and Martinsen (2015). Motivated individuals are those who are motivated by something within themselves, rather than by external factors. The word is also used to describe the willingness to put in more effort on a certain activity to get a specific reward. As an example, he described motivation as "how behavior is initiated, stimulated, maintained, directed, and what sort of subject responses are present in the organism while all of this is going on" in his paper on page 135 of the book.

Theoretical Framework

Herzberg's Two Factor Theory

Herzberg and his colleagues introduced the "Two Factor Theory" in 1959, which has since become one of the most well-known ideas in management (Amundsen and Martinsen 2015). Based on semi-independent interviews with 203 accountants and engineers from a Pittsburgh-based business, he conducted his research. The study's goal was to find out when participants felt good or bad about their jobs. To begin, participants were asked to describe in detail when they felt good about their work, and then to describe in great detail any times they felt negative about their work. Herzberg classified work aspects into important groups based on the responses to these questions. One of the major "motivators" and the secondary "hygiene" are both credited to him. According to this theory, extrinsic factors such as company policy, interpersonal connections, operating conditions, salary and reputation were cited as the primary source of hygienic aspects in employees' accounts of the harrowing experiences (adverse occasions). These aspects have to

do with the workplace and can rarely provide a genuine sense of active pleasure.

Job discontent occurs when these characteristics go below what the employee considers to be acceptable levels. The only thing a person can hope for when fulfilling the hygiene criteria is to keep them from experiencing job unhappiness and resulting in subpar work performance. Due to the hygiene aspects' lack of responsibility and accomplishment opportunities, employees have minimal possibility of self-actualization (Fauzilah, Noryati & Zaharah, 2011). On the other hand, motivators (like accomplishments and rewards) were linked to the job's substance and nature were primarily found in workers' accounts of the positive events that took place (positive events). Self-actualization and creativity have a greater probability of occurring when people are motivated by these factors (Fauzilah, Noryati & Zaharah, 2011)..

This means that the only way to keep your staff happy and motivated is to use motivational tools. There will be no work discontent if these variables are absent, but the outcome will be the same as that of those present. As a result, achieving job satisfaction requires completing two steps. By fulfilling the hygiene aspects of the employee, it is possible to remove job discontent to the point of 0% satisfaction (neutral state). Using the motivators, the employee's work happiness may be boosted from zero to one hundred percent. For Herzberg, satisfaction and dissatisfaction were not opposites; instead, Herzberg thought satisfaction and the factors that lead to it were distinct from those that lead to job dissatisfaction. Herzberg held that zero satisfaction was the opposite of satisfaction, while zero dissatisfaction was the opposite of dissatisfaction.

As a result of elucidating the many origins of workplace attitudes, the Two-Factor Theory has significantly contributed to management understanding. In industrial psychology, it was a significant source of inspiration for academics and created a ton of new ideas. For example, by stressing that management is not inspiring their employees' while focused just on hygienic aspects; Herzberg's theory sheds light on the substance of work motivation, showing that only a difficult task which contains the prospect of accomplishment may inspire individuals. Many studies indicate broad support for Herzberg's concept that variables contributing to job satisfaction (motivators) are distinct from and not simply opposing those leading to job unhappiness, as well as some support for Herzberg's theory (hygienes).

Expectancy Theory

The idea works best in a workplace when people's expectations are the only factors at play (Khiliji 2006). After being confronted with distinct selections among alternatives, people's knowledge of the concept turns to

the thought methods to go forward. People make a conscious effort to behave in a certain way, character values to choose preferred outcomes, man or woman expectations to achieve a specific final result and individual expectations about the possibility of being rewarded for achieving desired effects were discovered in literature as the theory's underpinning concepts. For Vroom, the motivation was about the link between the effort put in by a person and their perceived performance level and the anticipation that they will be rewarded for achieving desired results. To counter this, there should be an expectation that rewards will be forthcoming as this will have a significant impact on the strength of the motivational link, i.e., the intensity of the person's desire for an outcome and the belief that specific actions have the potential to lead to the desired result. To make the expectancy method easy:

Effort → Required performance → Desired outcome

Force = Valence × Expectancy

Expectancy measures how much people believe that changing their behavior will lead to the desired result. Valence measures how strongly people feel about their choice of outcome. The theory and its complexity in nature allow us to derive the finest suggestions for controlling it. We may try to find the preferred outcome that each bank values the most and set the goal and overall performance required to achieve it. The fact that the level of performance is realistic and achievable must also be remembered by management. After a certain amount of time has passed, control must determine the impacts on the performance that it favors. The techniques implemented at the site must not cause conflict between the expectations they wanted to establish and other militating components inside the workplace, one thing to keep in mind. Finally, the results must be eye-catching and compelling enough to pique interest in the preferred performance stage.

Empirical Framework

Employee Development and Employee Job Performance

Ahmad, Mohamed, and Manaf (2017) examined succession planning programs in Malaysian public sector organizations and found that succession planning contributed to employee development and enhanced confidence in organization management, which in turn improved individual as well as organizational performance. Rothwell, (2010) stated that succession planning plays a role in retaining employees by providing job development opportunities. Kraimer (2011) highlighted that career opportunities strengthen organizational support for employee development and performance. Similarly, Armstrong and West (2001) found that career development enhanced the satisfaction

of bank employees, which subsequently improved their performance

Ali and Mehreen (2018) indicated that career attitude is negatively related to employees desire to quit the firm. Hence, succession planning creates career paths for employees which directly enhance individual performance. Lack of advancement opportunities, poor work-life balance, inadequate reward and recognition were identified as common reasons for departure among all employees.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study examined the relationship between employee development as determinant of job performance in selected money deposit banks in Nigeria. The findings revealed that a significant relationship exists between employee development and job performance in the Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

The findings go in line with the conclusion of Prasadi & Morais (2019) who examines the impact of training and development on organizations performance: A study of managerial level employees in the Apparel Industry. The study has found a strong link between training and performance. The findings of the present research collaborate with the study of Owen's (2006) on empirical study on the relationship between training and organizational. This study found that training has a positive effect on commitment and turnover cognitions. Training employed by an organization which seeks to improve employee asset, upsurge mutuality, enables the employee to identify with the organization, and helps to reduce alternative employment options will increase employee's commitment to the organization.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study examines the correlation of Employee development and the measures of employee job performance (task accomplishment and service quality) in money deposit banks in Nigeria. From the findings, employee development significantly influences the measures of job performance. Career development in the deposit money banks is based on policies aimed at addressing the various needs of employees to enhance their job performance, reduce their intention to leave the organization and also to reduce the substantial cost involved in hiring and training new employees. The study concludes that employee development influences job performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study recommends that money deposit banks should implement career development policies towards effective succession planning. Management should exhaust all internal talent before considering external talent especially when making promotion decisions. Clear

career paths should be incorporated in the planning policies. Employee development opportunities should be available to all employees and ensure there is continuous skills improvement of the work force.

Gaps in Existing Literature

Studies have shown that on-the-job training for employees is an important component of HRM practices and enhances the human capital level in every organization. Training improves engagement, it allows for learning and development along their career ladder, which is vital to job performance. It was believed that professional training and development significantly impacted employees' performance in an organization most especially the banking industry. Training and development build competencies of employees to perform better on the job, prepare them to hold future positions and help them overcome underperformance. So far, existing literature on the impact of training and development on employee development, such as pharmaceutical companies; in Pakistan, health workers; in Kenya by Mangalore Pipe Industry. On the other hand, few domestically conducted studies on banking sectors in Nigeria, but to the best of my knowledge, studies on money deposit banks are insufficient. Hence, it is justifiable to research these sidelined organizations.

Similarly, the lack of sufficient empirical studies within the country justifies the need to conduct research in this area. This is because the findings from other studies might be quite different from what will be drawn from this particular study. The difference might originate from the nature of the data, organizational operations, and geographical location. Therefore, this particular study intends to fill this gap by laying out the impact of employee development and job performance in money deposit banks in Nigeria. At the same time, the study will give an insight on appropriate strategies to improve employee job performance and long-run productivity of an organization under the study.

REFERENCES

- Abba MT (2018). Effects of training and development on employee retention in Bauchi State Metropolis Banks. *Operational Research*, 4(1), 24-39.
- Abbott K (2012). Engaging the Public and the Private in Global Sustainability Governance. *International Affairs*, 88, 543-564.
- Adim CV, Ibekwe W, Akintokunbo OO (2018). Stress management and employee performance of Deposit Money Banks in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Ame. J. Humanit. Soc. Sci. Res. (AJHSSR)*, 2(12), 41-4.
- Ahmad RB, bin Mohamed AM, Manaf HBA (2017). The relationship between transformational leadership characteristic and succession planning program in the Malaysian public sector. *Int. J. Asian Soc. Sci.* 7(1), 19-30.
- Akintola BO, Adetomiwa B, Onifade FN (2022). Staff Training and Career Development among Library Staff in Federal Universities in Southwest, Nigeria. *International Information & Library Review*, 1-10.
- Amundsen S, Martinsen ØL (2015). Linking empowering leadership to job satisfaction, work effort, and creativity: The role of self-leadership and psychological empowerment. *J. Leader. Organ. Stud.* 22(3), 304-323.
- Armstrong A, Taylor S (2014). *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resources Management Practice*. London: Kogan Page
- Armstrong L, West J (2001). Banking, Technology Workers and Their Career Development. *Aus. J. Career Develop.* 10(1), 6-10.
- Armstrong M (2007). A handbook of human resource management practice. (10th ed.). London's Position within the Nomological Network, *J. Occupational and Organizational Psychol.* 80, 515-538.
- Baruch Y, Szűcs N, Gunz H (2015). Career studies in search of theory: The rise and rise of concepts. *Career Development International*, 20(1), 3-20. Berry, J. W., Kim, U., Power, S.,
- Brady MK, Cronin Jr, JJ (2001). Some new thoughts on conceptualizing perceived service quality: A hierarchical approach. *J. Market.* 65(3), 34-49.
- Campbell BA, Coff R, Krzyscynski D (2012). Rethinking sustained competitive advantage from human capital. *Academy of Management Review*, 37(3), 376-395.
- Chand M, Katou AA (2007). The impact of HRM practices on organisational performance in the Indian hotel industry. *Employee Relations*, 29(6), 576-594
- Ekerete PP (2005). Marketing of financial services: A case study of selected merchant banks in Nigeria. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 3, 271-287.
- Fauzah A, Noryati Y, Zaharah D (2011). The influence of skill levels on job performance of public service employees in Malaysia. *The Business and Management Review*, 1(1), 31- 40.
- Gronroos C (1990). Relationship approach to marketing in service contexts: The marketing and organizational behavior interface. *J. Bus. Res.* 20(1), 3-11.
- Hall-Ellis SD (2015). *Succession planning and staff development—a winning combination*. The New York: Bottom Line.
- Johnson RD, Pepper D, Adkins J, Emejom AA (2018). *Succession planning for large and small organizations: A practical review of professional business corporations in Succession planning*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan
- Kaya C, Ceylan B (2014). An empirical study on the role of career development programs in organizations and organizational commitment on job satisfaction of employees. *Ame. J. Bus. Manag.* 3(3), 178-191.
- Kelly D, Sugimoto CR (2013). A systematic review of interactive information retrieval evaluation studies, 1967-2006. *J. Ame. Soc. Info. Sci. Technol.* 64(4), 745-770.
- Kraimer ML, Seibert SE, Wayne SJ, Liden RC, Bravo J (2011). Antecedents and outcomes of organizational support for development: The critical role of career opportunities. *J. Applied Psychol.* 96(3), 485.
- Young M, Bujaki M (2018). Acculturation attitudes in plural societies. *Applied psychology*, 38(2), 185-206.